

From: [REDACTED] N [REDACTED] B [REDACTED]

To: The Clerk to the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

Subject: Memorandum on the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill

Date: 7th October 2021

I wish to respond to the request extended to the public by the Parliament of Ghana on 15th September 2021 asking for written memoranda on the three bills before Parliament. I hereby focus on the bill related to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill.

Honourable members of the select committee, I find it necessary to ask this question, humbly and respectfully: When ever did the use of the ‘anus’ become an orifice for sex, and to the extent of becoming a human right? Even animals do not do this when it comes to same sex. Why would we go so low as human beings? These are honest questions I ask myself repeatedly?

First and foremost, the first line of the national anthem says ‘God bless our homeland Ghana’... This God, from the biblical stance specifies that same sex and bestiality is an abomination and incurs curses on a nation (Leviticus 18: 22-25and Romans 1:26-28). Therefore, if as a nation we call forth on God to bless this land and turn around to do the very thing He detests, then we are ready to incur curses on our dear land, Ghana. If our fathers, who toiled with their blood to win for us our heritage, did not believe in a God who could help and bless this land, would they not find it necessary to acknowledge His ability to bless this great nation by starting the words of the nation’s anthem with God? In doing this our fathers duly acknowledged the importance and preeminence of God with regards to this great nation Ghana, thus we cannot override God in a matter as important as this.

Secondly, article 16 (1) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that, ‘Men and women of full age, without any limitation due to race, nationality or religion, have the right to marry and to found a family...’ It continues in subsection 3 to state that this ‘family is the natural and fundamental group unit of society and is entitled to protection by society and the State.’

This rightly maintains that a family then is a union between a man and a woman and this is the natural unit which must be protected by society and the state. This is exactly what the bill seeks to do by coming up with a law which would protect the natural unit and ensure Ghanaians are not deceptively indoctrinated into the LGBTQ+ act. The very sexual act committed by the LGBTQ+ community is unnatural and undermines the growth and development of the family system. Also, the Ghanaian cultural family values system obviously proscribes to the natural family unit consisting of a man and a woman, and not same-sex individuals. In protecting the family unit every effort must be put in place to ensure the fundamental structures are not destroyed. Moreso provisions in the bill, specifically clause 9 to 11, make provisions to help people who due to certain reasons have become victims to the same sex act.

Globally, LGBTQ+ people have access to various forms of healthcare and the cost of transitioning from one sex to the other is estimated to cost \$100,000

<https://edition.cnn.com/2015/07/31/health/transgender-costs-irpt/index.html>). Moreover, studies show an increase of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), among Men who have Sex with Men (MSM) in high-income countries (Chapin-Bardales et al., 2018) and especially in the US, where they continue to be a high-risk group (Mayer et al., 2021). It has been observed that lifetime cost estimates are helpful in measuring the economic burdens of a nation (Bingham et al., 2021). Currently, the lifetime treatment cost of an HIV infection is estimated at \$379,668 (in 2010 dollars) (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021). Again, a recent study with respect to the US, shows that the discounted lifetime cost estimate is \$490,045 in a most favourable scenario and \$326,411 in a least favourable scenario (Bingham et al., 2021). Can Ghana afford this? If the answer is even yes, is it not reasonable to use this to develop our infrastructure, education, health sectors, among others? Also, evidence from scientific research shows there is limited proof of a genetic cause for same-sex behaviours (Ganna et al., 2019).

It is interesting to note that the LGBTQ+ community claim they are in the minority and they are discriminated against. Yet evidence from countries where LGBTQ+ lifestyles have been legitimized show the reverse. People who maintain that they are heterosexuals, encounter a lot of trouble and persecution.

Some examples include the EU's threat to withhold aid from Poland for taking a stance against LGBTQ, and in the same news item, the Commission planning to sanction Hungary for passing a law which prohibits under 18 year olds from viewing homosexual content (<https://thehill.com/policy/international/europe/570960-eu-threatens-to-withhold-150m-in-aid-from-poland-over-anti-lgbtq>). Again, a female Labour party MP being threatened by the LGBTQ community over a statement made that only women have a cervix (<https://www.breitbart.com/politics/2021/09/20/labour-mp-backs-out-of-conference-after-threats-from-trans-activists/>). Evidence from the West shows that countries which oppose LGBTQ+ are more or less blackmailed (<https://www.euronews.com/2021/09/27/more-polish-regions-revoke-anti-lgbt-declarations-over-eu-funds-withdrawal>). We also hear of a case where a baker is fined by a court because his Christian principles would not allow him to design the cake to align with transgender beliefs (<https://www.npr.org/2021/06/17/1007594289/baker-fined-for-refusing-to-make-cake-for-transgender-woman>). Then again, it is announced that a court date has been set for a Finnish Minister of Parliament for tweeting a bible verse (<https://adfinternational.org/court-date-set-for-finnish-mp-charged-over-bible-tweet/>). With respect, where in Ghana, would it be allowed that a washroom or bathroom is shared by both men and women who are total strangers? This obviously is absurd but from the trends observed in the West, this is exactly what is happening (<https://www.theblaze.com/news/virginia-school-settles-with-gavin-grimm-aclu>). Finally, the Cooper report from the Ozanne foundation is seeking to push for the criminalization of 'conversion therapy' as against practices which help people transition from their biologically assigned genders (Ozanne Foundation, 2021). We cannot and must not, as a country, pass this on to the younger generations. Posterity would not forgive us.

As if these are not enough, we have LGBTQ+ community and advocates clearly realizing that if nations would oppose this, they must find a good way of pushing their agenda through by indoctrinating children. Evidence of this abounds in the West where children are allowed, with or without the consent of parents (depending on the laws within a particular jurisdiction), to change their sexual orientation (Family Research Council, 2020). The indoctrination is has to do with both the formal and informal educational sectors. The

informal education includes programmes on the media such as a children's show having a 222% increase in LGBTQ characters (<https://www.breitbart.com/entertainment/2021/06/11/shows-aimed-children-increase-lgbtq-characters-stories-two-years/>). Honourable members, some cartoon programmes our children watch on our televisions in our homes are filled with LGBTQ+ characters. The formal education aspect has to do with the Comprehensive Sexuality Education, where through all sorts of learning materials, children are supposed to be taught that sex is a right and that they can choose their sexual orientation without parental consent (Family Research Council, 2020; <https://www.comprehensivesexualityeducation.org/cse-materials-index/the-world-starts-with-me/>; <https://www.comprehensivesexualityeducation.org/cse-materials-index/>; https://www.comprehensivesexualityeducation.org/wp-content/uploads/Intl_Report060119.pdf).

Honourable members of the select committee, I humbly wish to reiterate that we must, as a nation, be bold to defend forever the cause of freedom and of right... we must resist oppressors' rule with all our will and might forever more. In my view as a Ghanaian, upholding all the above arguments, I believe that LGBTQ+ are mere lifestyle choices coupled with environmental factors which can be resolved if one is willing. Considering this, I fully endorse the PPHSRGFV Bill and encourage Parliament to fully pass it.

Signed:

Name: [REDACTED]

Title: Mrs.

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